

Fatigue Damage Characterization of Non-crimp Fabric Reinforced Reactive Thermoplastic Composites at Room and Low Temperatures

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Introduction

Overview

Materials and Experimental Details

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Overview of mean wind speed at 30m on Canadian territory [1]

Shell and spar made of glass fiber/epoxy or carbon fiber/epoxy laminates

Traditional wind turbine blade structure

Typical failure modes of wind turbine blades [2]

Brittle failure mode of FRP composites at low temperature

Characterization of FRP composites at low temperatures:

Author	Test condition	Main findings
Gong et al. [3]	Static tension UD Glass / epoxy RT and -196.15°C (77K)	The ultimate tensile strength, Young's modulus, and strain at failure increased at 77K.
Torabizadeh et al. [4]	Static tension, compression, shear UD Glass / epoxy RT, -20°C, -60°C	The strength and modulus both increased with decreasing temperature in all cases, while the strain at failure decreased.
Cormier et al. [5]	T-T fatigue tests with R=0.1 NCF Glass / epoxy RT and -40°C	The fatigue life improved significantly at lower temperature, with a steeper decrease of the S-N curves.
Shindo et al. [6]	T-T fatigue tests with R=0.1 Woven Glass / epoxy RT, -196.15°C and -269.15°C (4K)	The fatigue life increased at 77K compared to RT, followed by significant loss when further decreasing the temperature to 4K.
Bureau et al. [7]	T-T fatigue tests with R=0.1 Woven Glass / PP RT and -40°C	GF/PP composites had excellent fatigue performance at RT, which improved at -40°C.

Research gaps:

- Few studies focus on characterizing the performance of fiber-reinforced composites at low temperatures
 - Most studies do not consider damage evolution and failure mechanisms
 - Fewer studies on fiber-reinforced thermoplastics

Opportunity – Fiber-reinforced reactive thermoplastics:

- May offer improved toughness and durability at low temperatures
- Compatible with current liquid resin infusion processes for wind turbine blades
- Recyclable

Resin infused glass fiber-reinforced reactive thermoplastic for wind turbine blades

Objective 1

Establish non-destructive damage monitoring techniques at RT and LT, e.g., optical, thermographic [8]

Objective 2

Characterize stress-strain response at RT and LT

Objective 3

Study damage evolution and failure mechanisms under static and cyclic loading at RT and LT
 --- New Optical Imaging Technique
 --- Damage evolution, stiffness Degradation

Material system: UD-NCF glass (Saertex[®]) + Thermoplastic acrylic (Elium[®] 188 XO)

Fabric architecture:

Reactive thermoplastic acrylic resin:

Resin properties:

Low viscosity: 0.1 Pa·s

Polymerization time at RT: 2 hours

Post-cure dry-Tg: 123°C

Recyclable, low density, high strength and toughness

Component	Orientation	Material	Areal density
Tow	0	E-glass 2400 tex	
Supporting Fibers	90	E-glass 275 tex	943 gsm
Stitching	Tricot pattern	Polyester 110 dtex	

Resin Infusion Process and Workflow

VARTM set-up

Panel mold side

Panel vacuum bag side

Waterjet cutting machine

Test coupons

Mechanical test

Microscopic observation

Stacking sequence: $[0/90]_S, V_f = 48\%$

Sample dimension: 275L x 25W x 2.8T
(Rectangular specimen for static tests; Dog bone specimen for fatigue tests)

Type of test:

Static tension: 2mm/min, ASTM D 3039

Tension-Tension fatigue: Peak stress 50%-75%UTS, R=0.1, 5Hz, ASTM D 3479

Test temperature: RT and -50°C

DIC Speckle Patterns
(Strain measurement)

Test set-up for fatigue test

Stitch loops

Stacking sequence

Quasi-static test results

5 quasi-static tests were conducted at each temperature condition.

Laminate properties

	Tensile Strength (Mpa)	Modulus (GPa)	Strain at failure (%)	Strain at onset of failure (%)
RT	558.67 (± 13.69)	24.69 (± 0.42)	3.072 (± 0.17)	~ 0.60
-50°C	582.21 (± 22.46)	27.91 (± 0.44)	3.144 (± 0.26)	~ 0.26
Difference	+4.21%	+13.04%	+2.34%	-56.7%

Laminate stress-strain response (a) RT, (b) -50°C

- A near linear stress-strain behavior **at RT**;
- An obvious bilinear stress-strain response **at -50°C** with a transition stress in the range of 12% -15% UTS ($\sim 0.26\%$ strain).

Damage evolution of $[0/90]_s$ laminates at RT (Static)

Examples of 0° ply fiber tow

RT: (a) Undamaged stage, (b) 20% - 25% UTS,
(c) 50% - 55% UTS, (d) 70% - 75% UTS.

Microscopic observation of RT samples: (a) axial direction at 20%UTS,
(b) axial direction at 70%-75%UTS, (c) cross-section direction at 70%-75%UTS.

Damage evolution of $[0/90]_s$ laminates at -50°C (Static)

Examples of 0° ply fiber tow

Onset of 90° tow cracks

Examples of 90° ply fiber tow

Onset of 0° tow cracks

Damage development

-50°C : (a) Undamaged stage, (b) 10% - 15% UTS, (c) 35% - 40% UTS, (d) 70% - 75% UTS.

Microscopic observation of -50°C samples (a) axial direction at 20% UTS, (b) axial and cross-section direction at 50% UTS, (c) axial direction at 70%-75% UTS.

Fracture surface and damage evolution schematic (Static)

RT test specimen: (a) image of front fracture surface, (b) photomicrographs of front fracture surface, (c) photomicrographs of side fracture surface.

-50°C test specimen: (a) image of front fracture surface, (b) photomicrographs of front fracture surface, (c) photomicrographs of side fracture surface.

Schematic of damage evolution during static loading (only resin rich area between 90° fiber layers was shown)

Fatigue tests of $[0/90]_s$ laminates at -50°C (preliminary)

Rectangular specimen
(Failed at the end tab region)

Dog bone specimen
(Failed at the gauge length region)

Stiffness degradation at room temperature (50% UTS)

Strain measurement schemes:

- 1: Averaged strain of all areas (upper area + lower area)
- 2: Averaged strain of the upper area
- 3: Averaged strain of the lower area
- 4: Averaged line strain of all visual extensometers (1 + 2 + 3)
- 5: Line strain of the middle visual extensometer (2)

Damage development at RT (Fatigue, 75%UTS)

RT: (a) Undamaged stage, (b) 1st cycle,
(c) 12% N_f , (d) 97% N_f ($N_f = 875$)

Damage development at -50°C (Fatigue, 75%UTS)

-50°C : (a) Undamaged stage, (b) 1st cycle,
(c) 55% N_f , (d) 91% N_f ($N_f = 1375$)

1. The stress-strain response of UD-NCF glass fiber/acrylic composites at RT and -50°C is different (near linear vs obvious bilinear). However, similar damage modes were observed, i.e., 90° tow cracks, 0° tow cracks, matrix cracks, and interface cracks.
2. The ultimate tensile strength and Young's modulus increased at -50°C due to the increased resin strength and fiber-resin interface strength at low temperature.
3. At low temperature, damage tended to initiate at an early stage and was more advanced; however, there were fewer interactions between damage mechanisms causing stress relief and increased strain at failure.
4. For fatigue tests, the dog bone samples prevented premature failure, while the new strain measurement scheme enabled correlation of the damage evolution with stiffness degradation.
5. The damage development and failure mechanism of static tests and fatigue tests are different. The latter showed complicated damage modes at early stage (i.e., after 1 cycle). The damage evolution process at RT and -50°C is also different, and further validation is needed using microscope observation.

Future works:

1. Microscopic observations of failed specimens and interrupted specimens at different loading cycles to evaluate the failure mechanism and verify the observed damage modes at RT and -50 °C;
2. Perform fatigue tests at different stress levels (40% UTS to 80% UTS) to extract S-N data;
3. Correlate the observed damage modes with stiffness degradation and evaluate the crack density evolution during cyclic loading.

Acknowledgements

Thank you to all sponsors for this project!

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Thank You!